

Pricing Defaultable and Collateralized Derivatives

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new framework for valuing defaultable financial instruments with or without collateral arrangements. The framework characterizes default dependencies exogenously, and models collateral processes directly based on the fundamental principles of collateral agreements. We study the effect of collateralization on valuation, since the majority of OTC derivatives are collateralized. The model shows that a fully collateralized swap is risk-free, whereas a fully collateralized CDS is not equivalent to a risk-free one.

Key Words: asset pricing; credit risk modeling; one-way, two-way, multilateral credit risk; collateralization; comvariance; comrelation; correlation.

1 Introduction

A broad range of financial instruments bear credit risk. Credit risk may be one-way, two-way, or multilateral. Some instruments such as, loans, bonds, by nature contain only one-way credit risk because only the default risk of one party appears to be relevant, whereas some other instruments, such as, over the counter (OTC) derivatives, securities financing transactions (SFT), and credit derivatives, bear two-way or multilateral credit risk because two or more parties are susceptible to default risk. This paper mainly discusses two-way and multilateral credit risk modeling, with a particular focus on default dependency, as correlated credit risk is one of the greatest threats to global financial markets.

Central to the reduced-form models is the assumption that multiple defaults are independent conditional on the state of the economy. In reality, however, the default of one party might affect the default probabilities of other parties. Collin-Dufresne et al. (2003) and Zhang and Jorion (2007) find that a major credit event at one firm is associated with significant increases in the credit spreads of other firms. Giesecke (2004), Das et al. (2006), and Lando and Nielsen (2010) find that a defaulting firm can weaken the firms in its network of business links. These findings have important implications for the management of credit risk portfolios, where default relationships need to be explicitly modeled.

The main drawback of the conditionally independent assumption or the reduced-form models is that the range of default correlations that can be achieved is typically too low when compared with empirical default correlations (see Das et al. (2007)). The responses to correct this weakness can be generally classified into two categories: endogenous default relationship approaches and exogenous default relationship approaches.

The endogenous approaches include the contagion (or infectious) models and frailty models. The frailty models (see Duffie et al. (2009), Koopman et al. (2011), etc) describe default clustering based on some unobservable explanatory variables. In variations of contagion or infectious type models (see Davis and Lo (2001), Jarrow and Yu (2001), etc.), the assumption of conditional independence is relaxed and default intensities are made to depend on default events of other entities. Contagion and frailty models fill

an important gap but at the cost of analytic tractability. They can be especially difficult to implement for large portfolios.

The exogenous approaches (see Li (2000), Laurent and Gregory (2005), Hull and White (2004), Brigo et al. (2011), etc) attempt to link marginal default probability distributions to the joint default probability distribution through some external functions. Due to their simplicity in use, the exogenous approaches become very popular in practice.

Collateralization is one of the most important and widespread credit risk mitigation techniques used in derivatives transactions. According the ISDA (2012), 71% of all OTC derivatives transactions are subject to collateral agreements. The use of collateral in the financial markets has increased sharply over the past decade, yet the research on collateralized valuation is relatively sparse. Previous studies seem to turn away from direct and detailed modeling of collateralization (see Fujii and Takahashi (2012)). For example, Johannes and Sundaesan (2007), and Fujii and Takahashi (2012) characterize collateralization via a cost-of-collateral instantaneous rate (or stochastic dividend or convenience yield). Piterbarg (2010) regards collateral as a regular asset in a portfolio and uses the replication approach to price collateralized contracts.

This paper presents a new framework for valuing defaultable financial instruments with or without collateral arrangements. The framework characterizes default dependencies exogenously, and models collateral processes directly based on the fundamental principles of collateral agreements. Some well-known risky valuation models in the markets, e.g., the CDS model, the risky interest rate swap (IRS) model (Duffie and Huang (1996)), can be viewed as special cases of this framework, when the default dependencies are ignored.

We analyze the value of IRSs with two-way credit risk and look at how swap rates are affected by correlated default risk. Our study shows that counterparty default correlations have a relatively small impact on swap rates. Furthermore, we find that the value of a fully collateralized IRS is equal to the risk-free value. This conclusion is consistent with the current market practice in which market participants commonly assume fully collateralized swaps are risk-free.

We also study the value of CDS contracts with trilateral credit risk and assess how spreads depend on the risk of the buyer, seller, and reference entity in a CDS contract. In general, a CDS contract is used to transfer the credit risk of a reference entity from one party to another. The risk circularity that transfers one type of risk (reference credit risk) into another (counterparty credit risk) within the CDS market is a concern for financial stability. Some people claim that the CDS market has increased financial contagion or even propose an outright ban on these instruments.

The standard CDS pricing model in the market assumes that there is no counterparty risk. Although this oversimplified model may be accepted in normal market conditions, its reliability in times of distress has recently been questioned. In fact, counterparty risk has become one of the most dangerous threats to the CDS market. For some time now it has been realized that, in order to value a CDS properly, counterparty effects have to be taken into account (see ECB (2009)).

There is a significant increase in the use of collateral for CDS after the recent financial crises. Many people believe that, if a CDS is fully collateralized, there is no risk of failure to pay. Collateral posting regimes are originally designed and utilized for two-way risk products, e.g., IRS, but there are many reasons to be concerned about the success of collateral posting in offsetting the risk of CDS contracts. First, the value of CDS contracts tends to move very suddenly with big jumps, whereas the price movement of *IRS* contracts is far smoother and less volatile than *CDS*. Second, CDS spreads can widen very rapidly. Third, CDS contracts have many more risk factors than *IRS* contracts. In fact, our model shows that full collateralization cannot eliminate counterparty risk completely for a CDS.

This article also shows that the pricing process of a defaultable instrument normally has a backward recursive nature if the payoff can be positive or negative. Accordingly, we propose a backward induction approach for risky valuation. In contrast to the popular recursive integral solution (see Duffie and Huang (1996)), our backward induction method significantly simplifies the implementation. One can make use of the well-established algorithms, such as lattice/tree and regression-based Monte Carlo, to price a defaultable instrument.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Pricing two-way defaultable instruments is elaborated on in Section 2; valuing multilateral defaultable instruments is discussed in Section 3; the conclusions are presented in Section 4. All proofs and some detailed derivations are contained in the appendices.

2 Pricing Financial Instruments Subject to Two-way Credit Risk

We consider a filtered probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathcal{P})$ satisfying the usual conditions, where Ω denotes a sample space, \mathcal{F} denotes a σ -algebra, \mathcal{P} denotes a probability measure, and $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ denotes a filtration.

In the reduced-form approach, the stopping (or default) time τ_i of firm i is modeled as a Cox arrival process (also known as a doubly stochastic Poisson process) whose first jump occurs at default and is defined by,

$$\tau_i = \inf \left\{ t : \int_0^t h_i(s, Z_s) ds \geq H_i \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $h_i(t)$ or $h_i(t, Z_t)$ denotes the stochastic hazard rate or arrival intensity dependent on an exogenous common state Z_t , and H_i is a unit exponential random variable independent of Z_t .

It is well-known that the survival probability from time t to s in this framework is defined by

$$p_i(t, s) := P_i(\tau > s \mid \tau > t, Z_t) = \exp\left(-\int_t^s h_i(u) du\right) \quad (2a)$$

The default probability for the period (t, s) in this framework is given by

$$q_i(t, s) := P_i(\tau \leq s \mid \tau > t, Z_t) = 1 - p_i(t, s) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_t^s h_i(u) du\right) \quad (2b)$$

Three different recovery models exist in the literature. The default payoff is either i) a fraction of par (Madan and Unal (1998)), ii) a fraction of an equivalent default-free bond (Jarrow and Turnbull (1995)), or iii) a fraction of market value (Duffie and Singleton (1999)). The whole course of the recovery proceedings under the Bankruptcy and Insolvency act is a complex process that typically involves extensive negotiation and litigation. No model can fully capture all aspects of this process so, in practice, all models

involve trade-offs between different perspectives and views. In general, the choice for a certain recovery assumption is based on the legal structure of an instrument to be priced. For example, the recovery of market value (RMV) assumption is well matched to the legal structure of an IRS contract where, upon default close-out, valuation will in many circumstances reflect the replacement cost of the transaction, whereas the best default recovery assumption for a CDS is that the claim made in the event of the reference default equals a fraction of the face value of the underlying bond.

Two counterparties are denoted as A and B . The binomial default rule considers only two possible states: default or survival. Therefore, the default indicator Y_j for party j ($j=A, B$) follows a Bernoulli distribution, which takes value 1 with default probability q_j , and value 0 with survival probability p_j , i.e., $P\{Y_j = 0\} = p_j$ and $P\{Y_j = 1\} = q_j$. The marginal default distributions can be determined by the reduced-form models. The joint distributions of a multivariate Bernoulli variable can be easily obtained via the marginal distributions by introducing extra correlations.

Consider a pair of random variables (Y_A, Y_B) that has a bivariate Bernoulli distribution. The joint probability representations are given by

$$p_{00} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0) = p_A p_B + \sigma_{AB} \quad (3a)$$

$$p_{01} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1) = p_A q_B - \sigma_{AB} \quad (3b)$$

$$p_{10} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0) = q_A p_B - \sigma_{AB} \quad (3c)$$

$$p_{11} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1) = q_A q_B + \sigma_{AB} \quad (3d)$$

where $E(Y_j) = q_j$, $\sigma_j^2 = p_j q_j$, and $\sigma_{AB} := E[(Y_A - q_A)(Y_B - q_B)] = \rho_{AB} \sigma_A \sigma_B = \rho_{AB} \sqrt{q_A p_A q_B p_B}$ where ρ_{AB} denotes the default correlation coefficient, and σ_{AB} denotes the default covariance.

A critical ingredient of the pricing of a two-way defaultable instrument is the default settlement rules. There are two rules in the market. The *one-way payment rule* was specified by the early International Swap Dealers Association (ISDA) master agreement. The non-defaulting party is not obligated to compensate the defaulting party if the remaining market value of the instrument is positive for the defaulting

party. The *two-way payment rule* is based on current ISDA documentation. The non-defaulting party will pay the full market value of the instrument to the defaulting party if the contract has positive value to the defaulting party.

1.1 Risky valuation without collateralization

Consider a defaultable instrument that promises to pay a X_T from party B to party A at maturity date T , and nothing before date T . The payoff X_T may be positive or negative, i.e. the instrument may be either an asset or a liability to each party. All calculations are from the perspective of party A .

We divide the time period (t, T) into n very small time intervals (Δt) and use the approximation $\exp(y) \approx 1 + y$ provided that y is very small. The survival and the default probabilities for the period $(t, t + \Delta t)$ are given by

$$\hat{p}(t) := p(t, t + \Delta t) = \exp(-h(t)\Delta t) \approx 1 - h(t)\Delta t \quad (4a)$$

$$\hat{q}(t) := q(t, t + \Delta t) = 1 - \exp(-h(t)\Delta t) \approx h(t)\Delta t \quad (4b)$$

Suppose that the value of the instrument at time $t + \Delta t$ is $V(t + \Delta t)$ that can be an asset or a liability.

There are a total of four ($2^2 = 4$) possible states shown in Table 1.

The risky value of the instrument at time t is the discounted expectation of all the payoffs and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E \left\{ \exp(-r(t)\Delta t) \left[1_{V(t+\Delta t) \geq 0} \langle p_{00}(t) + \varphi_B(t)p_{01}(t) + \bar{\varphi}_B(t)p_{10}(t) + \varphi_{AB}(t)p_{11}(t) \rangle V(t + \Delta t) | \mathcal{F}_t \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + 1_{V(t+\Delta t) < 0} \langle p_{00}(t) + \bar{\varphi}_A(t)p_{01}(t) + \varphi_A(t)p_{10}(t) + \varphi_{AB}(t)p_{11}(t) \rangle V(t + \Delta t) | \mathcal{F}_t \right] \right\} \\ &\approx E \left\{ \exp \left[- \left(r(t) + 1_{V(t+\Delta t) \geq 0} l_B(t) + 1_{V(t+\Delta t) < 0} l_A(t) \right) \Delta t \right] V(t + \Delta t) | \mathcal{F}_t \right\} = E \left\{ \exp(-g(t)\Delta t) V(t + \Delta t) | \mathcal{F}_t \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (5a)$$

where

$$g(t) = r(t) + 1_{V(t+\Delta t) \geq 0} l_B(t) + 1_{V(t+\Delta t) < 0} l_A(t) \quad (5b)$$

$$l_B(t) = (1 - \varphi_B(t))h_B(t) + (1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(t))h_A(t) - (1 - \varphi_B(t) - \bar{\varphi}_B(t) + \varphi_{AB}(t))\rho_{AB}(t)\sqrt{h_A(t)h_B(t)} \quad (5c)$$

$$l_A(t) = (1 - \varphi_A(t))h_A(t) + (1 - \bar{\varphi}_A(t))h_B(t) - (1 - \varphi_A(t) - \bar{\varphi}_A(t) + \varphi_{AB}(t))\rho_{AB}(t)\sqrt{h_A(t)h_B(t)} \quad (5d)$$

where 1_Y is an indicator function that is equal to one if Y is true and zero otherwise, $E\{\bullet|\mathcal{F}_t\}$ is the expectation conditional on the \mathcal{F}_t , $r(t)$ is the risk-free short rate, and φ_i is the recovery rate.

The pricing equation above keeps terms of order Δt . All higher order terms of Δt are omitted. Similarly, we have

$$V(t + \Delta t) = E\left\{\exp(-g(t + \Delta t)\Delta t)V(t + 2\Delta t)\middle|\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right\} \quad (6)$$

Note that $\exp(-g(t)\Delta t)$ is $\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$ -measurable. By definition, an $\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$ -measurable random variable is a random variable whose value is known at time $t + \Delta t$. Based on the *taking out what is known* and *tower* properties of conditional expectation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E\left\{\exp(-g(t)\Delta t)V(t + \Delta t)\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} = E\left\{\exp(-g(t)\Delta t)E\left[\exp(-g(t + \Delta t)\Delta t)V(t + 2\Delta t)\middle|\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right]\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= E\left\{\exp\left(-\sum_{i=0}^1 g(t + i\Delta t)\Delta t\right)V(t + 2\Delta t)\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

By recursively deriving from t forward over T where $V(T) = X_T$ and taking the limit as Δt approaches zero, we obtain

$$V(t) = E\left\{G(t, T)X_T\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} = E\left\{\exp\left[-\int_t^T g(u)du\right]X_T\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (8)$$

We may think of $G(t, T)$ as the two-way risk-adjusted discount factor and $g(u)$ as the two-way risk-adjusted short rate. Equation (8) has a general form that applies in a particular situation where we assume that parties A and B have independent default risks, i.e. $\rho_{AB} = 0$ and $\varphi_{AB} = 0$. Thus, we have:

$$V(t) = E\left\{\bar{G}(t, T)X_T\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} = E\left\{\exp\left[-\int_t^T \bar{g}(u)du\right]X_T\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (9a)$$

where

$$\bar{g}(u) = r(u) + 1_{V(u) \geq 0} \bar{l}_B(u) + 1_{V(u) < 0} \bar{l}_A(u) \quad (9b)$$

$$\bar{l}_B(u) = (1 - \varphi_B(u))h_B(u) + (1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(u))h_A(u) \quad (9c)$$

$$\bar{l}_A(u) = (1 - \varphi_A(u))h_A(u) + (1 - \bar{\varphi}_A(u))h_B(u) \quad (9d)$$

Equation (9) is the same as equation (2.5') in Duffie and Huang (1996).

If we assume that a default may occur only on the payment date, the risky value of the instrument in a discrete-time setting is given by

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E\left\{D(t,T)\left[1_{X_T \geq 0}\langle p_{00}(t,T) + \varphi_B(T)p_{01}(t,T) + \bar{\varphi}_B(T)p_{10}(t,T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)p_{11}(t,T)\rangle X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\right.\right. \\ &\quad \left.\left.+ 1_{X_T < 0}\langle p_{00}(t,T) + \bar{\varphi}_A(T)p_{01}(t,T) + \varphi_A(T)p_{10}(t,T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)p_{11}(t,T)\rangle X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\right]\right\} \\ &= E\left[D(t,T)\left(1_{X_T \geq 0}k_B(t,T) + 1_{X_T < 0}k_A(t,T)\right)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\right] = E\left(K(t,T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\right) \end{aligned} \quad (10a)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} k_B(t,T) &= p_B(t,T)p_A(t,T) + \varphi_B(T)q_B(t,T)p_A(t,T) + \bar{\varphi}_B(T)p_B(t,T)q_A(t,T) \\ &\quad + \varphi_{AB}(T)q_B(t,T)q_A(t,T) + \sigma_{AB}(t,T)(1 - \varphi_B(T) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)) \end{aligned} \quad (10b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} k_A(t,T) &= p_B(t,T)p_A(t,T) + \varphi_A(T)q_A(t,T)p_B(t,T) + \bar{\varphi}_A(T)p_A(t,T)q_B(t,T) \\ &\quad + \varphi_{AB}(T)q_B(t,T)q_A(t,T) + \sigma_{AB}(t,T)(1 - \varphi_A(T) - \bar{\varphi}_A(T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)) \end{aligned} \quad (10c)$$

where $D(t,\tau)$ denotes the stochastic risk-free discount factor at t for the maturity T given by

$$D(t,T) = \exp\left[-\int_t^T r(u)du\right] \quad (10d)$$

We may think of $K(t,T)$ as the risk-adjusted discount factor, and $k_A(t,T)$ and $k_B(t,T)$ as the adjustment factors. Equation (10) tells us that the two-way risky price of a single-payment instrument can be expressed as the present value of the payoff discounted by a risk-adjusted discount factor that has a switching-type dependence on the sign of the payoff.

Equation (10) can be easily extended from one-period to multiple-periods. Suppose that a defaultable instrument has m cash flows. Let the m cash flows be represented as X_1, \dots, X_m with payment dates T_1, \dots, T_m . Each cash flow may be positive or negative. We have the following proposition.

Proposition 1: *The risky value of the multiple-payment instrument is given by*

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} K(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (11a)$$

where $t = T_0$ and

$$K(T_j, T_{j+1}) = D(T_j, T_{j+1})\left(1_{(X_{j+1} + V(T_{j+1})) \geq 0}k_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) + 1_{(X_{j+1} + V(T_{j+1})) < 0}k_A(T_j, T_{j+1})\right) \quad (11b)$$

where $k_A(T_j, T_{j+1})$ and $k_B(T_j, T_{j+1})$ are defined in Equation (10).

Proof: See the Appendix.

1.2 Risky valuation with collateralization

Collateralization is the most important and widely used technique in practice to mitigate credit risk. The posting of collateral is regulated by the Credit Support Annex (CSA) that specifies a variety of terms including the threshold, the independent amount, and the minimum transfer amount (MTA), etc. The threshold is the unsecured credit exposure that a party is willing to bear. The minimum transfer amount is the smallest amount of collateral that can be transferred. The independent amount plays the same role as the initial margin (or haircuts).

In a typical collateral procedure, a financial instrument is periodically marked-to-market and the collateral is adjusted to reflect changes in value. The collateral is called as soon as the mark-to-market (MTM) value rises above the given collateral threshold, or more precisely, above the threshold amount plus the minimum transfer amount. Thus, the collateral amount posted at time t is given by

$$C(t) = \begin{cases} V(t) - H(t) & \text{if } V(t) > H(t) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $H(t)$ is the collateral threshold. In particular, $H(t) = 0$ corresponds to full-collateralization¹; $H > 0$ represents partial/under-collateralization; and $H < 0$ is associated with over-collateralization. Full collateralization becomes increasingly popular at the transaction level. In this paper, we focus on full collateralization only, i.e., $C(t) = V(t)$.

The main role of collateral should be viewed as an improved recovery in the event of a counterparty default. According to Bankruptcy law, if there has been no default, the collateral is returned to the collateral giver by the collateral taker. If a default occurs, the collateral taker possesses the collateral. In other words, collateral does not affect the survival payment; instead, it takes effect on the default payment only.

¹ There are three types of collateralization: Full-collateralization is a process where the posting of collateral is equal to the current MTM value. Partial/under-collateralization is a process where the posting of collateral is less than the current MTM value. Over-collateralization is a process where the posting of collateral is greater than the current MTM value.

For a discrete one-period (t, u) economy, the posted collateral at time t is $C(t) = V(t)$. At time u , there are several possible states: i) Both A and B survive. The instrument value is equal to the market value $V(u)$; ii) Either or both counterparties A and B default. The instrument value is the future value of the collateral, i.e., $C(u) = V(t) / D(t, u)$ where we consider the time value of money only. Since the majority of the collateral is cash according to ISDA (2012), it is reasonable to consider the time value of money only for collateral assets. The large use of cash means that collateral is both liquid and not subject to large fluctuations in value. The value of the collateralized instrument at time t is the discounted expectation of all the payoffs and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E\left[D(t, u)(p_{00}(t, u)V(u) + p_{01}(t, u)C(u) + p_{10}(t, u)C(u) + p_{11}(t, u)C(u)) \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] \\ &= E\left[D(t, u)p_{00}(t, u)V(u) \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] + [1 - E(p_{00}(t, u) \mid \mathcal{F}_t)]V(t) \end{aligned} \quad (13a)$$

or

$$V(t) = E\left[D(t, s)p_{00}(t, s)V(s) \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] / E(p_{00}(t, s) \mid \mathcal{F}_t) \quad (13b)$$

If we assume that default probabilities are uncorrelated with interest rates and payoffs², we have

$$V(t) = E\left[D(t, s)V(s) \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (14)$$

Equation (14) is the formula for the risk-free valuation. Thus, we have the following proposition.

Proposition 2: *If a two-way risky instrument is fully collateralized, the risky value of the instrument is equal to the risk-free value, as shown in equation (14).*

Since an *IRS* is a typical two-way risky contract, Proposition 2 squares with the results of Johannes and Sundaesan (2007), and is also consistent with the current market practice in which market participants commonly assume fully collateralized swaps are risk-free and it is common to build models of swap rates assuming that swaps are free of counterparty risk.

² Moody's Investor's Service (2000) presents statistics that suggest that the correlations between interest rates, default probabilities, and recovery rates are very small and provides a reasonable comfort level for the uncorrelated assumption.

2 Pricing Financial Instruments Subject to Multilateral Credit Risk

The interest in the financial industry for the modeling and pricing of multilateral defaultable instruments arises mainly in two respects: in the management of credit risk at a portfolio level and in the valuation of credit derivatives. Central to the pricing and risk management of credit derivatives and credit risk portfolios is the issue of default relationships.

A CDS is normally used to transfer the credit risk of a reference entity between two counterparties. The contract reduces the credit risk of the reference entity but gives rise to another form of risk: *counterparty risk*. Since the dealers are highly concentrated within a small group, any of them may be too big to fail. The interconnected nature, with dealers being tied to each other through chains of OTC derivatives, results in increased contagion risk. Due to its concentration and interconnectedness, the CDS market seems to pose a systemic risk to financial market stability. In fact, the CDS is blamed for playing a pivotal role in the collapse of Lehman Brothers and the disintegration of AIG.

For years, a widespread practice in the market has been to mark CDS to market without taking the counterparty risk into account. The realization that even the most prestigious investment banks could go bankrupt has shattered the foundation of the practice. It is wiser to face frankly the real complexities of pricing a CDS than to indulge in simplifications that have proved treacherous. For some time now it has been realized that, in order to value a CDS properly, counterparty effects have to be taken into account.

The default indicator Y_j for firm j ($j = A$ or B or C) follows a Bernoulli distribution, which takes value 1 with default probability q_j , and value 0 with survival probability p_j . The joint probability representations of a trivariate Bernoulli distribution (see Teugels (1990)) are given by

$$p_{000} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0, Y_C = 0) = p_A p_B p_C + p_C \sigma_{AB} + p_B \sigma_{AC} + p_A \sigma_{BC} - \theta_{ABC} \quad (15a)$$

$$p_{100} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0, Y_C = 0) = q_A p_B p_C - p_C \sigma_{AB} - p_B \sigma_{AC} + q_A \sigma_{BC} + \theta_{ABC} \quad (15b)$$

$$p_{010} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1, Y_C = 0) = p_A q_B p_C - p_C \sigma_{AB} + q_B \sigma_{AC} - p_A \sigma_{BC} + \theta_{ABC} \quad (15c)$$

$$p_{001} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0, Y_C = 1) = p_A p_B q_C + q_C \sigma_{AB} - p_B \sigma_{AC} - p_A \sigma_{BC} + \theta_{ABC} \quad (15d)$$

$$p_{110} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1, Y_C = 0) = q_A q_B p_C + p_C \sigma_{AB} - q_B \sigma_{AC} - q_A \sigma_{BC} - \theta_{ABC} \quad (15e)$$

$$p_{101} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0, Y_C = 1) = q_A p_B q_C - q_C \sigma_{AB} + p_B \sigma_{AC} - q_A \sigma_{BC} - \theta_{ABC} \quad (15f)$$

$$p_{011} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1, Y_C = 1) = p_A q_B q_C - q_C \sigma_{AB} - q_B \sigma_{AC} + p_A \sigma_{BC} - \theta_{ABC} \quad (15g)$$

$$p_{111} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1, Y_C = 1) = q_A q_B q_C + q_C \sigma_{AB} + q_B \sigma_{AC} + q_A \sigma_{BC} + \theta_{ABC} \quad (15h)$$

where

$$\theta_{ABC} := E((Y_A - q_A)(Y_B - q_B)(Y_C - q_C)) \quad (15i)$$

Equation (15) tells us that the joint probability distribution of three defaultable parties depends not only on the bivariate statistical relationships of all pair-wise combinations (e.g., σ_{ij}) but also on the trivariate statistical relationship (e.g., θ_{ABC}). θ_{ABC} was first defined by Deardorff (1982) as *comvariance*, who use it to correlate three random variables that are the value of commodity net imports/exports, factor intensity, and factor abundance in international trading.

We introduce the concept of *comvariance* into credit risk modeling arena to exploit any statistical relationship among multiple random variables. Furthermore, we define a new statistic, *comrelation*, as a scaled version of comvariance (just like correlation is a scaled version of covariance) as follows:

Definition 1: For three random variables X_A , X_B , and X_C , let μ_A , μ_B , and μ_C denote the means of X_A , X_B , and X_C . The comrelation of X_A , X_B , and X_C is defined by

$$\zeta_{ABC} = \frac{E[(X_A - \mu_A)(X_B - \mu_B)(X_C - \mu_C)]}{\sqrt[3]{E|X_A - \mu_A|^3 \times E|X_B - \mu_B|^3 \times E|X_C - \mu_C|^3}} \quad (16)$$

According to the Holder inequality, we have

$$|E((X_A - \mu_A)(X_B - \mu_B)(X_C - \mu_C))| \leq E|(X_A - \mu_A)(X_B - \mu_B)(X_C - \mu_C)| \leq \sqrt[3]{E|X_A - \mu_A|^3 \times E|X_B - \mu_B|^3 \times E|X_C - \mu_C|^3} \quad (17)$$

Obviously, the comrelation is in the range of [-1, 1]. Given the comrelation, Equation (15i) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{ABC} &:= E((Y_A - q_A)(Y_B - q_B)(Y_C - q_C)) = \zeta_{ABC} \sqrt[3]{E|Y_A - q_A|^3 \times E|Y_B - q_B|^3 \times E|Y_C - q_C|^3} \\ &= \zeta_{ABC} \sqrt[3]{p_A q_A (p_A^2 + q_A^2) p_B q_B (p_B^2 + q_B^2) p_C q_C (p_C^2 + q_C^2)} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where $E(Y_j) = q_j$ and $E|Y_j - q_j|^3 = p_j q_j (p_j^2 + q_j^2)$, $j=A, B, \text{ or } C$.

If we have a series of n measurements of X_A , X_B , and X_C written as x_{Ai} , x_{Bi} and x_{Ci} where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, the sample *comrelation coefficient* can be obtained as:

$$\zeta_{ABC} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_{Ai} - \mu_A)(x_{Bi} - \mu_B)(x_{Ci} - \mu_C)}{\sqrt[3]{\sum_{i=1}^n |x_{Ai} - \mu_A|^3 \times \sum_{i=1}^n |x_{Bi} - \mu_B|^3 \times \sum_{i=1}^n |x_{Ci} - \mu_C|^3}} \quad (19)$$

More generally, we define the *comrelation* in the context of n random variables as

Definition 2: For n random variables X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n , let μ_i denote the mean of X_i where $i=1, \dots, n$. The *comrelation* of X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n is defined as

$$\zeta_{12\dots n} = \frac{E[(X_1 - \mu_1)(X_2 - \mu_2) \cdots (X_n - \mu_n)]}{\sqrt[n]{E|X_1 - \mu_1|^n \times E|X_2 - \mu_2|^n \cdots \times E|X_n - \mu_n|^n}} \quad (20)$$

The *correlation* is just a specific case of the *comrelation* where $n = 2$. Again, the *comrelation* $\zeta_{12\dots n}$ is in the range of $[-1, 1]$ according to the Holder inequality.

2.1 Risky valuation without collateralization

Recovery assumptions are important for pricing credit derivatives. If the reference entity under a CDS contract defaults, the best assumption, as pointed out by J. P. Morgan (1999), is that the recovered value equals the recovery rate times the face value plus accrued interest³. In other words, the recovery of par value assumption is a better fit upon the default of the reference entity, whereas the recovery of market value assumption is a more suitable choice in the event of a counterparty default.

Let valuation date be t . Suppose that a CDS has m scheduled payments. Let each payment be represented as $X_i = -sN\delta(T_{i-1}, T_i)$ with payment dates T_1, \dots, T_m where $i=1, \dots, m$, $\delta(T_{i-1}, T_i)$ denotes the accrual factor for period (T_{i-1}, T_i) , N denotes the notional/principal, and s denotes the CDS premium. Party A pays the premium/fee to party B if reference entity C does not default. In return, party B agrees to pay the

³ In the market, there is an average accrual premium assumption, i.e., the average accrued premium is half the full premium due to be paid at the end of the premium.

protection amount to party A if reference entity C defaults before the maturity. We have the following proposition.

Proposition 3: *The value of the multiple-payment CDS is given by*

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right) X_i \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right] + \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-2} O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right) \Omega(T_{i-1}, T_i) R(T_{i-1}, T_i) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (21a)$$

where $t = T_0$ and

$$O(T_j, T_{j+1}) = 1_{(V(T_{j+1}) + X_{j+1}) \geq 0} \phi_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) + 1_{(V(T_{j+1}) + X_{j+1}) < 0} \phi_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) \quad (21b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) = & \{p_A(T_j, T_{j+1})p_B(T_j, T_{j+1})p_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1})p_B(T_j, T_{j+1})p_C(T_j, T_{j+1})\varphi_A(T_{j+1}) \\ & + p_A(T_j, T_{j+1})q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})p_C(T_j, T_{j+1})\bar{\varphi}_A(T_{j+1}) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1})q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})p_C(T_j, T_{j+1})\varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) \\ & + p_C(T_j, T_{j+1})\sigma_{AB}(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \varphi_A(T_{j+1}) - \bar{\varphi}_A(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \\ & + \sigma_{AC}(T_j, T_{j+1})[p_B(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \varphi_A(T_{j+1})) + q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})(\bar{\varphi}_A(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}))] \\ & + \sigma_{BC}(T_j, T_{j+1})[p_A(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \bar{\varphi}_A(T_{j+1})) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1})(\varphi_A(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}))] \\ & + \theta_{ABC}(T_j, T_{j+1})(-1 + \bar{\varphi}_A(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_A(T_{j+1}))\}D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (21c)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) = & \{p_A(T_j, T_{j+1})p_B(T_j, T_{j+1})p_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1})p_B(T_j, T_{j+1})p_C(T_j, T_{j+1})\bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) \\ & + p_A(T_j, T_{j+1})q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})p_C(T_j, T_{j+1})\varphi_B(T_{j+1}) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1})q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})p_C(T_j, T_{j+1})\varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) \\ & + p_C(T_j, T_{j+1})\sigma_{AB}(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1}) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \\ & + \sigma_{AC}(T_j, T_{j+1})[p_B(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1})) + q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})(\varphi_B(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}))] \\ & + \sigma_{BC}(T_j, T_{j+1})[p_A(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1})) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1})(\bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}))] \\ & + \theta(T_j, T_{j+1})(-1 + \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_B(T_{j+1}))\}D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (21d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(T_j, T_{j+1}) = & \{p_A(T_j, T_{j+1})p_B(T_j, T_{j+1})q_C(T_j, T_{j+1}) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1})p_B(T_j, T_{j+1})q_C(T_j, T_{j+1})\bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) \\ & + p_A(T_j, T_{j+1})q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})q_C(T_j, T_{j+1})\varphi_B(T_{j+1}) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1})q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})q_C(T_j, T_{j+1})\varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) \\ & + q_C(T_j, T_{j+1})\sigma_{AB}(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1}) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \\ & - \sigma_{AC}(T_j, T_{j+1})[p_B(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1})) + q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})(\varphi_B(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}))] \\ & - \sigma_{BC}(T_j, T_{j+1})[p_A(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1})) + q_A(T_j, T_{j+1})(\bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}))] \\ & + \theta_{ABC}(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) - \varphi_B(T_{j+1}))\}D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (21e)$$

where $R(T_j, T_{j+1}) = (N(1 - \varphi_C(T_{j+1})) - \alpha(T_j, T_{j+1}))$, $\alpha(T_j, T_{j+1}) = sN\delta(T_S, T)/2$, and $X_i = -sN\delta(T_j, T_{j+1})$.

Proof: See the Appendix.

We may think of $O(t, T)$ as the risk-adjusted discount factor for the premium and $\Omega(t, T)$ as the risk-adjusted discount factor for the default payment. Proposition 3 says that the pricing process of a multiple-payment instrument has a backward nature since there is no way of knowing which risk-adjusted discounting rate should be used without knowledge of the future value. Only on the maturity date, the value

of an instrument and the decision strategy are clear. Therefore, the evaluation must be done in a backward fashion, working from the final payment date towards the present. This type of valuation process is referred to as backward induction.

Proposition 3 provides a general form for pricing a CDS. Applying it to a particular situation in which we assume that counterparties *A* and *B* are default-free, i.e., $p_j = 1$, $q_j = 0$, $\rho_{kl} = 0$, and $\varsigma_{ABC} = 0$, where $j=A$ or B and $k, l=A, B, \text{ or } C$, we derive the following corollary.

Corollary 1: *If counterparties A and B are default-free, the value of the multiple-payment CDS is given by*

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] + \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-2} O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)\Omega(T_{i-1}, T_i)R(T_{i-1}, T_i) | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[D(t, T_i)p_C(t, T_i)X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] + \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[D(t, T_i)p_C(t, T_{i-1})q_C(T_{i-1}, T_i)R(T_{i-1}, T_i) | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where $O(T_{i-1}, T_i) = D(T_{i-1}, T_i)p_C(T_{i-1}, T_i)$; $\Omega(T_{i-1}, T_i) = D(T_{i-1}, T_i)q_C(T_{i-1}, T_i)$.

The proof of this corollary becomes straightforward according to Proposition 3 by setting $\rho_{kl} = 0$, $\varphi_{AB} = 0$, $\varsigma_{ABC} = 0$, $p_j = 1$, $q_j = 0$, $p_C(t, T_i) = \prod_{g=0}^{i-1} p(T_g, T_{g+1})$, and $D(t, T_i) = \prod_{g=0}^{i-1} D(T_g, T_{g+1})$.

If we further assume that the discount factor and the default probability of the reference entity are uncorrelated and the recovery rate φ_C is constant, we have

Corollary 2: *Assume that i) counterparties A and B are default-free, ii) the discount factor and the default probability of the reference entity are uncorrelated; iii) the recovery rate φ_C is constant; the value of the multiple-payment CDS is given by*

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m P(t, T_i)\bar{p}_C(t, T_{i-1})\bar{q}_C(T_{i-1}, T_i)(N(1 - \varphi_C) - \alpha(T_{i-1}, T_i)) - \sum_{i=1}^m P(t, T_i)\bar{p}_C(t, T_i)sN\delta(T_{i-1}, T_i) \quad (23)$$

where $P(t, T_i) = E[D(t, T_i) | \mathcal{F}_t]$ denotes the bond price, $\bar{p}_C(t, T_i) = E[p_C(t, T_i) | \mathcal{F}_t]$, $\bar{q}_C(t, T_i) = 1 - \bar{p}_C(t, T_i)$, $\bar{p}(t, T_{i-1})\bar{q}(T_{i-1}, T_i) = \bar{p}(t, T_{i-1}) - \bar{p}(t, T_i)$.

This corollary is easily proved according to Corollary 1 by setting $E[XY | \mathcal{F}_t] = E[X | \mathcal{F}_t]E[Y | \mathcal{F}_t]$ when *X* and *Y* are uncorrelated. *Corollary 2 is the formula for pricing CDS in the market.*

Our methodology can be extended to the cases where the number of parties $n \geq 4$. A generating function for the (probability) joint distribution (see details in Teugels (1990)) of n -variate Bernoulli can be expressed as

$$p^{(n)} = \begin{bmatrix} p_n & -1 \\ q_n & 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} p_{n-1} & -1 \\ q_{n-1} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \dots \otimes \begin{bmatrix} p_1 & -1 \\ q_1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \sigma^{(n)} \quad (24)$$

where \otimes denotes the Kronecker product; $p^{(n)} = \{p_k^{(n)}\}$ and $\sigma^{(n)} = \{\sigma_k^{(n)}\}$ are vectors containing 2^n components: $p_k^{(n)} = p_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n}$, $k = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^n k_i 2^{i-1}$, $k_i \in \{0, 1\}$; $\sigma_k^{(n)} = \sigma_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n} = E\left(\prod_{i=1}^n (Y_i - q_i)^{k_i}\right)$.

2.2 Risky valuation with collateralization

According to the ISDA (2012), almost all CDSs are fully collateralized. Many people believe that full collateralization can eliminate counterparty risk completely for CDS.

We assume that a CDS is fully collateralized, i.e., the posting of collateral is equal to the amount of the current *MTM* value: $C(t) = V(t)$. For a discrete one-period (t, u) economy, there are several possible states at time u : i) A , B , and C survive with probability p_{000} . The instrument value is equal to the market value $V(u)$; ii) A and B survive, but C defaults with probability p_{001} . The instrument value is the default payment $R(u)$; iii) For the remaining cases, either or both counterparties A and B default. The instrument value is the future value of the collateral $V(t)/D(t, u)$ (Here we consider the time value of money only). The value of the collateralized instrument at time t is the discounted expectation of all the payoffs and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E\left\{D(t, u)\left[p_{000}(t, u)V(u) + p_{001}(t, u)R(u)\right.\right. \\ &\quad \left.\left.+ (p_{100}(t, u) + p_{010}(t, u) + p_{110}(t, u) + p_{101}(t, u) + p_{011}(t, u) + p_{111}(t, u))V(t)/D(t, u)\right]\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (25a) \\ &= E\left\{D(t, u)\left(p_{000}(t, u)V(s) + p_{001}(t, u)R(u)\right) + (1 - p_{000}(t, u) - p_{001}(t, u))V(t)\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} &E\left[\left(p_A(t, u)p_B(t, u) + \sigma_{AB}(t, u)\right)\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right]V(t) \\ &= E\left\{D(t, u)\left(p_C(t, u)V(u) + q_C(t, u)R(u)\right)\left(p_A(t, u)p_B(t, u) + \sigma_{AB}(t, u)\right)\right. \\ &\quad \left.+ D(t, u)\left(V(u) - R(u)\right)\left(p_B(t, u)\sigma_{AC}(t, u) + p_A(t, u)\sigma_{BC}(t, u) - \theta_{ABC}(t, u)\right)\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (25b) \end{aligned}$$

If we assume that $(p_A(t,u)p_B(t,u) + \sigma_{AB}(t,u))$ and $D(t,u)(p_C(t,u)V(u) + q_C(t,u)R(u))$ are uncorrelated, we have

$$V(t) = V^F(t) + \xi_{ABC}(t,u) / \psi_{AB}(t,u) \quad (26a)$$

where

$$V^F(t) = E\{D(t,u)[p_C(t,u)V(u) + q_C(t,u)R(u)] | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (26b)$$

$$\psi_{AB}(t,u) = E\{[p_A(t,u)p_B(t,u) + \sigma_{AB}(t,u)] | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (26c)$$

$$\xi_{ABC}(t,u) = E\{[D(t,u)(p_B(t,u)\sigma_{AC}(t,u) + p_A(t,u)\sigma_{BC}(t,u) - \theta_{ABC}(t,u))(V(u) - R(u))] | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (26d)$$

The first term $V^F(t)$ in equation (26) is the counterparty-risk-free value of the CDS and the second term is the exposure left over under full collateralization, which can be substantial.

Proposition 4: *If a CDS is fully collateralized, the risky value of the CDS is NOT equal to the counterparty-risk-free value, as shown in equation (26).*

Proposition 4 or equation (26) provides a theoretical explanation for the failure of full collateralization in the CDS market. It tells us that under full collateralization the risky value is in general not equal to the counterparty-risk-free value except in one of the following situations: i) the market value is equal to the default payment, i.e., $V(u) = R(u)$; ii) firms A , B , and C have independent credit risks, i.e., $\rho_{ij} = 0$ and $\varsigma_{ABC} = 0$; or iii) $p_B\sigma_{AC} + p_A\sigma_{BC} = \theta_{ABC}$.

3 Conclusion

This article presents a new valuation framework for pricing financial instruments subject to credit risk. In particular, we focus on modeling default relationships. Some well-known risky valuation models in the market can be viewed as special cases of this framework, when the default dependencies are ignored.

To capture the default relationships among more than two defaultable entities, we introduce a new statistic: *comrelation*, an analogue to correlation for multiple variables, to exploit any multivariate statistical relationship. Our research shows that accounting for default correlations and comrelations becomes

important, especially under market stress. The existing valuation models in the credit derivatives market, which take into account only pair-wise default correlations, may underestimate credit risk and may be inappropriate.

We study the sensitivity of the price of a defaultable instrument to changes in the joint credit quality of the parties. For instance, our analysis shows that the effect of default dependence on CDS premia from large to small is the correlation between the protection seller and the reference entity, the correlation between the protection buyer and the reference entity, and the correlation between the protection buyer and the protection seller.

The model shows that a fully collateralized swap is risk-free, while a fully collateralized CDS is not equivalent to a risk-free one. Therefore, we conclude that collateralization designed to mitigate counterparty risk works well for financial instruments subject to two-way credit risk, but fails for ones subject to multilateral credit risk.

Appendix

Proof of Proposition 1. Let $t = T_0$. On the first cash flow payment date T_1 , let $V(T_1)$ denote the market value of the instrument excluding the current cash flow X_1 . According to Equation (10), we have

$$V(t) = E[K(T_0, T_1)(X_1 + V(T_1)) | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (\text{A1})$$

Similarly, we have

$$V(T_1) = E[K(T_1, T_2)(X_2 + V(T_2)) | \mathcal{F}_{T_1}] \quad (\text{A2})$$

Note that $K(T_0, T_1)$ is \mathcal{F}_{T_1} -measurable. According to *taking out what is known* and *tower* properties of conditional expectation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E[K(T_0, T_1)(X_1 + V(T_1)) | \mathcal{F}_t] = E[K(T_0, T_1)X_1 | \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &\quad + E\left\{K(T_0, T_1)\left[E(K(T_1, T_2)X_2 | \mathcal{F}_{T_1}) + E(K(T_1, T_2)V(T_2) | \mathcal{F}_{T_1})\right] | \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= E[K(T_0, T_1)X_1 | \mathcal{F}_t] + E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^1 K(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_2 | \mathcal{F}_t\right] + E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^1 K(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)V(T_2) | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A3})$$

By recursively deriving from T_2 forward over T_m , where $V(T_m) = X_m$, we have

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} K(T_j, T_{j+1}) \right) X_i \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (\text{A4})$$

Proof of Proposition 3. Let $t = T_0$. On the first payment date T_1 , let $V(T_1)$ denote the market value of the CDS excluding the current cash flow X_1 . There are a total of eight ($2^3 = 8$) possible states shown in Table A1. The risky price is the discounted expectation of the payoffs and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E \left\{ \left[\mathbf{1}_{(V(T_1)+X_1) \geq 0} \left((p_{000}(T_0, T_1) + p_{100}(T_0, T_1) \bar{\varphi}_B(T_1) + p_{010}(T_0, T_1) \varphi_B(T_1) + p_{110}(T_0, T_1) \varphi_{AB}(T_1)) (V(T_1) + X_1) \right) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right] \right. \\ &\quad + \mathbf{1}_{(V(T_1)+X_1) < 0} \left((p_{000}(T_0, T_1) + p_{100}(T_0, T_1) \varphi_A(T_1) + p_{010}(T_0, T_1) \bar{\varphi}_A(T_1) + p_{110}(T_0, T_1) \varphi_{AB}(T_1)) (V(T_1) + X_1) \right) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right] \\ &\quad + (p_{001}(T_0, T_1) + p_{101}(T_0, T_1) \bar{\varphi}_B(T_1) + p_{011}(T_0, T_1) \varphi_B(T_1) + p_{111}(T_0, T_1) \varphi_{AB}(T_1)) R(T_s, T_1) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \Big] D(t, T) \Big\} \\ &= E \left\{ \left[O(T_0, T_1) (V(T_1) + X_1) + \Omega(T_0, T_1) R(T_s, T_1) \right] \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A5a})$$

where

$$O(T_0, T_1) = \mathbf{1}_{(V(T_1)+X_1) \geq 0} \phi_B(T_0, T_1) + \mathbf{1}_{(V(T_1)+X_1) < 0} \phi_A(T_0, T_1) \quad (\text{A5b})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_A(T_0, T_1) &= \{ p_A(T_0, T_1) p_B(T_0, T_1) p_C(T_0, T_1) + q_A(T_0, T_1) p_B(T_0, T_1) p_C(T_0, T_1) \varphi_A(T_1) \\ &\quad + p_A(T_0, T_1) q_B(T_0, T_1) p_C(T_0, T_1) \bar{\varphi}_A(T_1) + q_A(T_0, T_1) q_B(T_0, T_1) p_C(T_0, T_1) \varphi_{AB}(T_1) \\ &\quad + p_C(T_0, T_1) \sigma_{AB}(T_0, T_1) (1 - \varphi_A(T_1) - \bar{\varphi}_A(T_1) + \varphi_{AB}(T_1)) \\ &\quad + \sigma_{AC}(T_0, T_1) [p_B(T_0, T_1) (1 - \varphi_A(T_1)) + q_B(T_0, T_1) (\bar{\varphi}_A(T_1) - \varphi_{AB}(T_1))] \\ &\quad + \sigma_{BC}(T_0, T_1) [p_A(T_0, T_1) (1 - \bar{\varphi}_A(T_1)) + q_A(T_0, T_1) (\varphi_A(T_1) - \varphi_{AB}(T_1))] \\ &\quad + \theta_{ABC}(T_0, T_1) (-1 + \bar{\varphi}_A(T_1) - \varphi_{AB}(T_1) + \varphi_A(T_1)) \Big\} D(T_0, T_1) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A5c})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_B(T_0, T_1) &= \{ p_A(T_0, T_1) p_B(T_0, T_1) p_C(T_0, T_1) + q_A(T_0, T_1) p_B(T_0, T_1) p_C(T_0, T_1) \bar{\varphi}_B(T_1) \\ &\quad + p_A(T_1, T_1) q_B(T_0, T_1) p_C(T_0, T_1) \varphi_B(T_1) + q_A(T_0, T_1) q_B(T_0, T_1) p_C(T_0, T_1) \varphi_{AB}(T_1) \\ &\quad + p_C(T_0, T_1) \sigma_{AB}(T_0, T_1) (1 - \varphi_B(T_1) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_1) + \varphi_{AB}(T_1)) \\ &\quad + \sigma_{AC}(T_0, T_1) [p_B(T_0, T_1) (1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_1)) + q_B(T_0, T_1) (\varphi_B(T_1) - \varphi_{AB}(T_1))] \\ &\quad + \sigma_{BC}(T_0, T_1) [p_A(T_0, T_1) (1 - \varphi_B(T_1)) + q_A(T_0, T_1) (\bar{\varphi}_B(T_1) - \varphi_{AB}(T_1))] \\ &\quad + \theta_{ABC}(T_0, T_1) (-1 + \bar{\varphi}_B(T_1) - \varphi_{AB}(T_1) + \varphi_B(T_1)) \Big\} D(T_0, T_1) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A5d})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(T_0, T) &= \{ p_A(T_0, T) p_B(T_0, T) q_C(T_0, T) + q_A(T_0, T) p_B(T_0, T) q_C(T_0, T) \bar{\varphi}_B(T_1) \\ &\quad + p_A(T_0, T) q_B(T_0, T) q_C(T_0, T) \varphi_B(T_1) + q_A(T_0, T) q_B(T_0, T) q_C(T_0, T) \varphi_{AB}(T_1) \\ &\quad + q_C(T_0, T) \sigma_{AB}(T_0, T) (1 - \varphi_B(T_1) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_1) + \varphi_{AB}(T_1)) \\ &\quad - \sigma_{AC}(T_0, T) [p_B(T_0, T) (1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_1)) + q_B(T_0, T) (\varphi_B(T_1) - \varphi_{AB}(T_1))] \\ &\quad - \sigma_{BC}(T_0, T) [p_A(T_0, T) (1 - \varphi_B(T_1)) + q_A(T_0, T) (\bar{\varphi}_B(T_1) - \varphi_{AB}(T_1))] \\ &\quad + \theta_{ABC}(T_0, T) (1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_1) + \varphi_{AB}(T_1) - \varphi_B(T_1)) \Big\} D(T_0, T) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A5e})$$

Similarly, we have

$$V(T_1) = E\left\{[O(T_1, T_2)(X_2 + V(T_2)) + \Omega(T_1, T_2)R(T_1, T_2)] | \mathcal{F}_{T_1}\right\} \quad (\text{A6})$$

Note that $O(T_0, T_1)$ is \mathcal{F}_{T_1} -measurable. According to *taking out what is known* and *tower* properties of conditional expectation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E\left\{[O(T_0, T_1)(X_1 + V(T_1)) + \Omega(T_0, T_1)R(T_0, T_1)] | \mathcal{F}_t\right\} = E[O(T_0, T_1)X_1 | \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &\quad + E[\Omega(T_0, T_1)R(T_0, T_1) | \mathcal{F}_t] + E\left\{O(T_0, T_1)E\left\{[O(T_1, T_2)(X_2 + V(T_2)) + \Omega(T_1, T_2)R(T_1, T_2)] | \mathcal{F}_{T_1}\right\} | \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^2 E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i\right] + \sum_{i=1}^2 E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-2} O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)\Omega(T_{i-1}, T_i)R(T_{i-1}, T_i)\right] \\ &\quad + E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^1 O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)V(T_2) | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A7})$$

By recursively deriving from T_2 forward over T_m , where $V(T_m) = X_m$, we have

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] + \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-2} O(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)\Omega(T_{i-1}, T_i)R(T_{i-1}, T_i) | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (\text{A8})$$

References

Arora, Navneet, Priyank Gandhi, and Francis A. Longstaff (2009), “Counterparty credit risk and the credit default swap market,” Working paper, UCLA.

Collin-Dufresne, P., R. Goldstein, and J. Helwege (2003), “Is credit event risk priced? Modeling contagion via the updating of beliefs,” Working paper, Haas School, University of California, Berkeley.

Das, S., D. Duffie, N. Kapadia, and L. Saita (2007), “Common failings: How corporate defaults are correlated,” *Journal of Finance*, 62: 93-117.

Davis, M., and V. Lo (2001), “Infectious defaults,” *Quantitative Finance*, 1: 382-387.

Deardorff, Alan V. (1982): “The general validity of the Heckscher-Ohlin Theorem,” *American Economic Review*, 72 (4): 683-694.

Duffie, D., A. Eckner, G. Horel, and L. Saita (2009), “Frailty correlated default,” *Journal of Finance*, 64: 2089-2123.

FinPricing, 2019, Market data services <https://finpricing.com/lib/FxAccumulator.html>

Giesecke, K. (2004), “Correlated default with incomplete information,” *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 28: 1521-1545.

Jarrow, R., and S. Turnbull (1995), “Pricing derivatives on financial securities subject to credit risk,” *Journal of Finance*, 50: 53-85.

Johannes, M. and S. Sundareshan (2007), “The impact of collateralization on swap rates,” *Journal of Finance*, 62: 383-410.

Koopman, S., A. Lucas, and B. Schwaab (2011), “Modeling frailty-correlated defaults using many macroeconomic covariates,” *Journal of Econometrics*, 162: 312-325.

Lando, D. and M. Nielsen (2010), “Correlation in corporate defaults: contagion or conditional independence?” *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 19: 355-372.

Laurent, J. and J. Gregory (2005), “Basket default swaps, CDOs and factor copulas,” *Journal of Risk*, 7: 03-122.

Longstaff, F., and E. Schwartz (2001): “Valuing American options by simulation: a simple least-squares approach,” *The Review of Financial Studies*, 14 (1): 113-147.

Madan, D., and H. Unal (1998), "Pricing the risks of default," *Review of Derivatives Research*, 2: 121-160.

O'Kane, D. and S. Turnbull (2003), "Valuation of credit default swaps," *Fixed Income Quantitative Credit Research*, Lehman Brothers, QCR Quarterly, Q1/Q2: 1-19.

Piterbarg, V. (2010), "Funding beyond discounting: collateral agreements and derivatives pricing," *Risk Magazine*, 2010 (2): 97-102.

Teugels, J. (1990), "Some representations of the multivariate Bernoulli and binomial distributions," *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, 32: 256-268.